

EXPLORING THE INFLUENCE OF AN INNOVATIVE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT ON THE IMPROVEMENT OF ASSESSMENT QUALITY AT RIVERS STATE UNIVERSITY

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Abstract: This study explores the influence of an innovative learning environment on the improvement of assessment quality at Rivers State University. A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. Three research questions and three null hypotheses tested at a 0.05 alpha level were employed to execute the study. The study population comprised 5800 undergraduate students and 260 lecturers at Rivers State University. A sample of 200 students and 40 lecturers was drawn using stratified random sampling to ensure representation across departments. The data for the study were collected with a researcher-made instrument titled: "Innovative Learning Environment and Improvement of Assessment Quality Questionnaire (ILEIAQQ)". The instrument contained two sections: Section A: Demographic information, and Section B elicited information from the Innovative Learning Environment, Assessment Quality using the 4-point Likert scale of strongly agree, agree, disagree, and strongly disagree. The face and content validity of the instrument were ascertained by the experts in the Department of Measurement and Evaluation. A structured questionnaire was administered to students and lecturers to measure their perceptions of the innovative learning environment and its impact on assessment quality. The instruments were validated by experts in educational research and test measurement, and a pilot study was conducted to determine reliability using Cronbach's alpha, which yielded a coefficient of 0.82, indicating high reliability. Data were collected in two phases. First, questionnaires were distributed to students and lecturers within the selected faculties. Quantitative data from the questionnaires were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation). The findings revealed that the adoption and expansion of innovative learning practices remain essential for strengthening the assessment quality at Rivers State University. With adequate institutional support, investment in digital infrastructure, and continuous professional development for lecturers and students, innovative learning environments can catalyze sustainable improvement in higher education assessment. It recommends that Rivers State University invest in modern ICT facilities, reliable internet connectivity, and functional e-learning platforms to support innovative assessment practices.

Keywords: Innovative, Learning Environment, Assessment, and Assessment Quality

Introduction

Education is crucial in shaping human behavior, instilling virtues and positive values in individuals to promote positive living and contribute to societal development. The core purpose of education is to produce citizens who are well-cultured and whose behaviors align with accepted social norms. Higher education is widely regarded as a platform where individual potential is identified, nurtured, and developed for the benefit of both individuals and society. Universities serve as a platform to advance efforts in achieving societal, aspirational, and educational goals. To ensure that educational goals are achieved, there is a need to evaluate the individuals to ascertain if there are changes in behavior. Also, to ensure that the learning methods are effective and that the learning objectives are achieved.

This brings to the fore the need for assessment. Assessment is a critical tool in the evaluation of learning outcomes. It is a systematic evaluation of the students' knowledge, skills and competencies to ascertain if the learning objectives are achieved. Assessment serves as a tool to evaluate students' learning progress, inform stakeholders, classify students into educational tracks, and influence decisions about school effectiveness, ultimately affecting efficiency, equity, and individual well-being (Teixeira & Tavano 2024). In the same vein, Abduraxmonov and Ismailov (2022) opined that assessment is a critical tool for evaluating student progress, guiding instructional decisions, and promoting equity and inclusion within educational systems. Therefore, educational institutions adopt various educational assessments to achieve effective learning outcomes. Din et al. (2023) opined that educational assessment should include formative, diagnostic, and summative assessments, and these significantly contribute to the development, the improvement of students' learning, improve their critical thinking, and boost their confidence in skill development across diverse educational fields. Conversely, Munaroh (2024) enumerated the various educational assessments to include diagnostic, formative, summative, selective, and placement assessments, as well as assessment of learning, assessment for learning, and assessment as learning. The researcher further classified the techniques into test and non-test methods. Also, as noted by Daniyeye (2024), identified assessment methods include traditional assessments (e.g., multiple-choice tests), performance-based assessments (e.g., projects and portfolios), and technology-enhanced assignments (e.g., digital simulations and e-portfolios), each serving different evaluation purposes in education. According to Johnson (2016), assessment methods include interviews, observations, document reviews, manual testing, and automated testing efforts, which are utilized in educational institutions to review and evaluate performance and learning outcomes effectively.

These findings underscore the need for effective and quality assessment methods not only in universities but also in all educational institutions. Thus, assessment methods measure students' progress, guide educational decisions, and provide valuable feedback to students, parents, and education institutions. Others are ensuring accountability within educational institutions and providing informed decisions regarding course selection, thereby optimizing their educational paths (Zhou 2023).

Therefore, the quality of assessment in higher education is a critical determinant of the students' learning outcomes, academic standards and institutional credibility. The quality of assessment is a factor that ensures that students acquire the necessary knowledge, skills and competencies to excel in their various career choices. Irrespective of the strategies or the tools used in the assessment of students, there is a need to ensure a quality assessment method. Quality assessment is to ensure that the products or services meet the established standards. The fundamental attributes of a good assessment encompass validity, reliability, and objectivity. It is important to recognize that different assessments are suited to varying learning needs and provide clear insights into their performance and achievements, ultimately enhancing their educational experience and engagement (Gurban,2023).

It is imperative to mention that the advent of the fourth industrial revolution has questioned the validity of the traditional assessment quality. This has led to a growing concern about transforming traditional learning environments into innovative learning environments to enhance pedagogical effectiveness. An innovative learning environment is a learning environment that jettison or move beyond the traditional learning setting, is flexible, dynamic and integrates technology in the process of teaching and learning. An innovative learning environment is designed to adapt various learning styles and activities, fostering students' involvement, active participation, and ownership of learning as well as the integration of technology in teaching and learning (Patricx, 2017: Turmudi & Dahlan, 2023: Magen-Nagar & Steinberger, 2017). These environments foster collaboration, creativity, and critical thinking, which are essential for addressing the challenges of the 21st century.

It is pertinent to mention some of the innovative learning environments that are transforming higher educational landscapes by integrating diverse methodologies and technologies that enhance active students' engagement and learning outcomes. Innovative learning environments in higher education include gamification, flipped learning, personalized learning, project-based learning, peer teaching, remote learning platforms, virtual reality settings, online and blended learning, and the use of multimedia resources (Niyazova & Nelidova, 2024; Rayoo & Winkelmann, 2021: Geitz et al., 2023 and Papaioannou et al., 2023). Gamification incorporates game elements into learning: flipped learning encourages students to study content at home and participate in interactive activities in class; personalized learning focuses on individuals' experiences and needs; adaptive learning technologies use AI to modify learning paths based on students' experiences, while virtual reality offers simulations of real-world scenarios that promote experiential learning. These environments foster active engagement, collaboration, and critical thinking among students, preparing them for real-world challenges and enhancing their learning experience. It also enhances academic performance through various pedagogical strategies and applications of real-world context, which are critical for 21st century skills.

Despite the immense benefits of the innovative learning environment and the increasing adoption in higher education, especially in the developed world. It appears that Nigerian universities are yet to leverage on it. At Rivers State University, it seems that assignments often rely on traditional methods that may not fully capture students' competences and foster deeper learning. Also there are empirical

research on the innovative learning environment but little or no on the improvement of quality assessment, especially in Rivers State University. This has prompted the researcher to explore the influence of the innovative learning environment on the improvement of assessment quality in Rivers State University. The researcher is interested in determining the influence of gamification, flipped learning, personalized learning, and adaptive learning on the assessment quality at Rivers State University.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this study was to explore the influence of an innovative learning environment on the improvement of assessment quality in Rivers State University. Specifically, the objective of the study is to:

1. To determine the extent to which the innovative learning environment enhances the quality of assessment in Rivers State University
2. Determine the ways in which lecturers integrate innovative learning strategies to improve the validity and authenticity of assessment practices
3. Examine the challenges hindering the effective use of innovative learning environments in strengthening assessment practices at Rivers State University.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. To what extent does the innovative learning environment enhance the quality of assessment at Rivers State University?
2. In what ways do lecturers integrate innovative learning strategies to improve the validity and authenticity of their assessment practices?
3. What challenges hinder the effective use of innovative learning environments in strengthening assessment practices at Rivers State University?

Methodology

A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. Three research questions and three null hypotheses tested at a 0.05 alpha level were employed to execute the study. The study population comprised 5800 undergraduate students and 260 lecturers at Rivers State University. A sample of 200 students and 40 lecturers was drawn using stratified random sampling to ensure representation across departments. The data for the study were collected with a researcher-made instrument titled: "Innovative Learning Environment and Improvement of Assessment Quality Questionnaire (ILEIAQQ)". The instrument contained two sections: Section A: Demographic information, and Section B elicited information from the Innovative Learning Environment, Assessment Quality using the 4-point Likert scale of strongly agree, agree, disagree, and strongly disagree. The face and content validity of the instrument were ascertained by the experts in the Department of Measurement and Evaluation. A structured questionnaire was administered to students and lecturers to measure their perceptions of the innovative learning environment and its impact on assessment quality. The instruments were validated by experts in educational research and test measurement, and a pilot study was conducted to

determine reliability using Cronbach’s alpha, which yielded a coefficient of 0.82, indicating high reliability. Data were collected in two phases. First, questionnaires were distributed to students and lecturers within the selected faculties. Quantitative data from the questionnaires were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) to summarize the responses and inferential statistics (t-test and ANOVA) to determine the significant differences in the perceptions of assessment quality across the groups.

Results

Research Question One: To what extent does the innovative learning environment enhance the quality of assessment at Rivers State University?

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Innovative Learning Environment as Enhancing the Quality of Assessment in Rivers State University

S/N	Item/Statement	Lecturer		Remarks	Student		Remarks
		Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
		N=40			N=200		
1	Innovative learning environments promote fairness in assessment practices.	3.3	10.40	High	3.2	57.09	High
2	The use of innovative learning strategies helps align assessments with real-life applications	3.0	8.60	High	3.2	56.2	High
3	Student-centered learning environments improve the reliability of the assessment outcomes.	3.3	10.34	High	3.4	63.7	High
4	Collaborative and problem-based learning contribute to a deeper understanding, which enhances the quality of the assessment.	3.4	11.40	High	3.2	57.5	High
5	The integration of digital technologies has improved the transparency of assessment practices.	3.1	8.86	High	3.3	59.1	High
6	Innovative learning encourages the development of higher-order thinking skills as assessed in examinations.	3.4	11.29	High	3.2	56.6	High
7	Continuous assessment methods are more effective when supported by innovative learning environments.	3.0	8.54	High	3.1	55.8	High
8	The use of e-assessment platforms ensures timely and accurate feedback for students.	3.1	9.30	High	3.5	65.3	High
9	Innovative learning practices reduce bias and subjectivity in the assessment.	3.2	9.41	High	3.2	59.1	High
10	Overall, innovative learning environments significantly enhance the quality of assessment at Rivers State University.	3.3	11.14	High	3.2	56.2	High
Grand Mean		3.20	0.15		3.30	0.12	

Table 1 shows that the grand mean of (3.20 and 3.30) are the innovative learning environment that enhances the quality of assessment in Rivers State University is above the criterion mean of 2.5. This

result indicated that the 10 items are the innovative learning environment that enhance the quality of assessment in Rivers State University.

Research Question Two: In what ways do lecturers integrate innovative learning strategies to improve the validity and authenticity of their assessment practices?

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Respondents on how lecturers integrated innovative learning strategies to improve the validity and authenticity of assessment practices.

Lecturers Students N=40 N=200							
S/N	Item/Statement	Mean	SD	Remark	Mean	SD	Remark
1	I integrate problem-based learning to ensure that assessments measure real-world problem-solving skills.	3.1	9.43	High	3.2	56.6	High
2	I use project-based tasks to enhance the authenticity of the student assessment.	3.3	9.85	High	3.1	55.8	High
3	I apply case studies and simulations to test students' ability to transfer knowledge into practice.	3.0	8.60	High	3.5	65.3	High
4	I employ digital platforms (e.g., LMS, online quizzes) to improve the transparency and reliability of the assessment.	3.2	9.41	High	3.2	59.1	High
5	I design assessments that encourage collaboration and teamwork among students.	3.2	9.92	High	3.2	56.2	High
6	I use authentic assessment tools (e.g., portfolios, presentations, and reflective journals) in evaluating students.	3.3	11.14	High	3.0	52.5	High
7	I integrate formative assessment strategies (e.g., feedback, peer evaluation) to enhance the validity of the results.	3.4	11.29	High	3.2	56.2	High
8	I align the assessment tasks with the learning outcomes to ensure accuracy and fairness.	3.0	8.54	High	3.4	63.4	High
9	I regularly update my assessment strategies to reflect current innovations in teaching and learning.	3.1	9.30	High	3.2	56.2	High
10	Overall, my integration of innovative learning strategies has improved the validity and authenticity of the student assessment practices.	3.2	9.41	High	3.4	64.2	High
Weighted Average		3.20	0.13		3.20	0.15	

Table 2 shows that the grand mean of (3.20 and 3.20) is how lecturers integrate innovative learning strategies to improve the validity and authenticity of assessment practices is above the criterion mean of 2.5. This result indicated that the 10 items are how lecturers integrate innovative learning strategies to improve the validity and authenticity of assessment practices.

Research Question Three: What challenges hinder the effective use of innovative learning environments in strengthening assessment practices at Rivers State University?

Table 3: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the challenges hindering the effective use of innovative learning environments in strengthening assessment practices at Rivers State University.

S/N	Item/Statement	Mean	SD	Remark	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Limited access to digital tools and infrastructure hinders the effective use of innovative learning environments in assessment.	3.3	10.4	High	3.2	56.2	High
2	Poor internet connectivity reduces the efficiency of online or technology-based assessments.	3.0	8.60	High	3.4	63.4	High
3	Inadequate funding limits the adoption of innovative learning strategies for assessment.	3.3	10.34	High	3.2	56.2	High
4	Lack of regular training for lecturers and students affects the effective use of innovative assessment methods.	3.4	11.40	High	3.4	64.2	High
5	Resistance to change among lecturers and students makes it difficult to adopt new learning and assessment innovations.	3.1	8.86	High	3.3	59.0	High
6	Large class sizes limit the effective integration of innovative assessment practices	3.2	9.92	High	3.2	57.1	High
7	Insufficient technical support affects the sustainability of the digital assessment tools.	3.2	9.41	High	3.2	56.2	High
8	Limited awareness of innovative assessment methods constrains their effective use.	3.0	8.60	High	3.4	63.7	High
9	Time constraints make it difficult for lecturers to design and implement authentic and innovative assessments.	3.3	9.85	High	3.2	57.5	High
10	Institutional policies do not adequately support the consistent use of innovative learning environments in assessment.	3.1	9.43	High	3.3	59.1	High
Grand Mean		3.20	0.14		3.30	0.09	

Table 3 shows that the grand mean of (3.20 and 3.30) are challenges that hinder the effective use of innovative learning environments in strengthening assessment practices at Rivers State University is above the criterion mean of 2.5. This result indicated that the 10 items are that challenges hinder the effective use of innovative learning environments in strengthening assessment practices at Rivers State University.

Discussion of the Findings

An innovative learning environment significantly enhances the quality of assessment at Rivers State University

The findings revealed that the innovative learning environment significantly enhances the quality of assessment at Rivers State University. Both students and lecturers agreed that innovative practices—such as project-based learning, collaborative tasks, digital assessment platforms, and continuous formative evaluation—contribute to improving the fairness, validity, and authenticity of assessments. This suggests that innovative learning environments not only transform classroom interactions but also strengthen the standards of evaluation in higher education. This finding supports Redecker (2013), who emphasized that technology-enabled assessment systems foster transparency, consistency, and accountability in evaluating student performance. The results also showed that innovative environments encourage higher-order thinking skills such as critical analysis, creativity, and problem-solving, which are now embedded in assessment practices. This aligns with Jonassen (2000), who argued that learner-centered and constructivist environments foster deeper engagement, thereby enabling assessments to capture more complex learning outcomes.

Lecturers at Rivers State University integrate multiple innovative learning strategies to enhance the validity and authenticity of assessment practices.

The findings revealed that lecturers at Rivers State University integrated multiple innovative learning strategies to enhance the validity and authenticity of their assessment practices. Prominent among these were problem-based learning, project work, case studies, and simulations, which ensured that the assessment tasks mirrored real-world contexts. By engaging students in authentic tasks, lecturers provide opportunities for learners to demonstrate skills beyond rote memorization, thereby increasing the credibility and meaningfulness of the assessment outcomes. This finding resonates with Gulikers, Bastiaens, and Kirschner (2004), who argued that authentic assessment tasks must reflect the complexity of professional practice to be valid. The study also showed that lecturers increasingly use digital tools such as online quizzes, e-portfolios, and learning management systems to improve transparency, feedback, and reliability in assessment. The integration of such platforms enabled timely feedback and reduced the subjectivity often associated with traditional paper-based examinations. This aligns with Redecker (2013), who observed that ICT-enabled assessments enhance both efficiency and validity through automation and feedback mechanisms.

Several challenges hinder the effective use of innovative learning environments in strengthening assessment practices at Rivers State University.

The findings showed that several challenges hinder the effective use of innovative learning environments in strengthening assessment practices at Rivers State University. These challenges can be grouped into infrastructural, pedagogical, and institutional barriers, which collectively limit the consistent application of innovation in assessment. A major challenge identified was limited access to digital infrastructure, such as computers, e-learning platforms, and reliable internet connectivity. Respondents emphasized that these inadequacies often disrupted e-assessments and restricted the

integration of technology-driven evaluation tools. This finding supports Adeoye and Aladesanmi (2020), who noted that infrastructural deficits remain one of the most persistent barriers to implementing digital and innovative assessment strategies in Nigerian universities. Another significant challenge was the lack of adequate training and capacity building for lecturers and students. Many lecturers acknowledged difficulties in designing authentic assessment tasks due to insufficient professional development opportunities. Similarly, some students lacked the technical competence to fully engage with the digital assessment tools. This is consistent with Boud and Falchikov (2007), who stressed that without appropriate training, even well-designed innovative strategies may fail to enhance assessment quality.

Conclusion

This study has shown that the innovative learning environment plays a significant role in improving the quality of assessment at Rivers State University. Evidence from both students and lecturers indicates that integrating innovative practices—such as problem-based learning, project work, collaborative engagement, digital tools, and formative assessment strategies—enhances the validity, authenticity, fairness, and transparency of assessments. These approaches not only provide students with opportunities to demonstrate higher-order thinking skills but also align evaluation processes more closely with real-life applications and global best practices. However, the study also identified notable challenges—including infrastructural limitations, poor internet connectivity, inadequate training, resistance to change, and large class sizes—that hinder the full realization of innovative learning environments in assessment. Despite these challenges, it is evident that innovative learning environments significantly contribute to raising assessment standards, ensuring reliability, and fostering deeper and more meaningful learning outcomes. In conclusion, the adoption and expansion of innovative learning practices remain essential for strengthening the assessment quality at Rivers State University. With adequate institutional support, investment in digital infrastructure, and continuous professional development for lecturers and students, innovative learning environments can catalyze sustainable improvement in higher education assessment.

Recommendations

1. Rivers State University should invest in modern ICT facilities, reliable internet connectivity, and functional e-learning platforms to support innovative assessment practices.
2. Regular training workshops and professional development programs should be organized to equip lecturers with the skills to design and implement valid and authentic assessments using innovative strategies.
3. Students should be given orientation and hands-on training on the use of digital assessment tools, collaborative learning platforms, and authentic assessment methods to enhance their engagement and competence.

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